

SMUGGLING IN THE MODERN WORLD**Utebaev Salamat Maksetbay ugli**

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Abstract. This work is devoted to the topic of smuggling in the modern world. In today's Russia it acquires enormous scales. First of all it is due to illegal exports and imports. Smuggling sizes were studied in different periods. Various causes of contraband spreading are considered in this paper. The article also discusses methods of combating smuggling at the present stage. They have been developed in different directions. The work carried out is summarized and the basic conclusions on this issue are formulated.

Keywords: Smuggling, illegal goods, trace transfer operations, law enforcement, lack of customs control, break the law, huge losses.

КОНТРАБАНДА В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ

Аннотация. Данная работа посвящена теме контрабанды в современном мире. В современной России она приобретает огромные масштабы. В первую очередь это связано с незаконным экспортом и импортом. Размеры контрабанды изучались в разные периоды. В статье рассматриваются различные причины распространения контрабанды. Также в статье рассматриваются методы борьбы с контрабандой на современном этапе. Они развивались в разных направлениях. Подведены итоги проделанной работы и сформулированы основные выводы по данному вопросу.

Ключевые слова: Контрабанда, нелегальные товары, следовые операции, правоприменение, отсутствие таможенного контроля, нарушение закона, огромные убытки.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study is to study the status of the black market of the country, to find out what influences smuggling and how police fight against it.

The subject of smuggling is of immediate interest not only in Russia, but all over the world. The only difference is in what amount it exists on the territory of a country. Contraband is illegal movement of goods, values and other items across the state border. Contraband is harmful for all spheres of the society. Therefore, the state develops more slowly than it could.

In Russia, the shadow side of the economy is growing from year to year. This is the consequence not only of illegal exports to Russia but imports into foreign countries as well. In today's market a significant proportion of goods and services is contraband. In Russia, it measures more than 50%, which speaks about underdeveloped law enforcement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Causes of trafficking - the emergence of monopolies, excessive customs duties and charges, and low levels of taxation and lack of control of customs authorities. In addition, the low level of welfare of the population, who are forced to engage in illegal activities to somehow provide themselves.

Total there are several types of contraband. First, drug smuggling. Secondly, trafficking in cultural property. In Russia, both species reach considerable proportions.

In the third millennium there are many ways to prevent smuggling. First, many countries including Russia have toughened punishments for such an activity. Second, many companies offer a full range of juridical and bookkeeping tracking entities and entrepreneurs that allow you to trace all transfer operations and detect violations of the law. New technical equipment (electronic declaration) is being designed to help trace the path of illegal goods as soon as possible and prevent them from entering the territory of another country or on the market of the country. Specialized departments on developing strategies for capturing criminals are being set up.

RESULTS

A large number of smuggling goods were especially found on the borders with Eastern Europe including the countries - participants of the Customs Union. To date, most illegally transported various types of goods. And every year this activity is gaining momentum. According to many experts, the most common way of shadow movements of goods are in the areas bordering with Poland, Lithuania and Kazakhstan. Perhaps this is because in these customs zones less carefully conducted customs control of goods.

The Customs Union only strengthened the development of new gray schemes. Imperfection of the regulatory framework of the Customs Union of Belarus, Kazakhstan and Russia creates opportunities for economic crime - smuggling, gray import-export schemes, illegal capital outflow and corruption. In 2012 through companies registered in Belarus, Russia has lost about \$ 15 billion, and by the company from Kazakhstan - \$10 billion. The scheme used by hackers is simple. Payment for nonexistent goods, allegedly brought to Russia from Belarus or Kazakhstan, is carried out on the basis of waybills. In this way it is impossible to trace the real delivery because of lack of customs control.

Smuggling is growing from year to year as it is one of the easiest ways to earn big money. According to statistics, every second transporter understands and consciously breaks the law to enrich his pocket as much as possible. Thus a vicious circle is formed, in which each is looking for his benefit, not realizing that the country's economy bears huge losses due to the existence of the black market which, in turn, degrades citizens' life quality of this country.

DISCUSSION

During 2011, 641 criminal charges were instituted, 116 cases of which were related to illegal movement of vehicles, 90 cases – to drugs. It is only during January-March 2012 that law enforcement authorities identified and stopped 60,063 drug offenses. It is also known that nearly 70% of the gold in Russia is smuggled. According to customs statistics there's almost 2.3-fold increase in the number of identified facts of drug smuggling over the last year.

Russia, in its turn was hoping to reduce the size of contraband after WTO accession. Russian customs officers believed that after joining the WTO, illegal import would lose its positions and the scope accepted. But after Russia's accession to the World Trade Organization, there are much fewer obstacles as to the movement of goods, which increase their import to the Russian market. It means that it raises the level of competition in the market among foreign products which leads to a greater extent to increasing smuggling rather than reducing it.

CONCLUSIONS

However, as expected, in the beginning there will not be positive dynamics of development after WTO accession in Russia, but in the long term we will see improvements in all aspects, including the reduction of smuggling. Since the regulatory framework of the WTO is much stronger than the Customs Union framework, it will possibly be able to set the Russian trade flows in order, without prejudice to the national economy.

Thus, in the course of our study, we found out that smuggling takes a rather large part of the economy and prevents it from full developing. And even joining any Customs Unions and various world organizations does not provide complete elimination of smuggling.

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